

EFFECT OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE RATE MOVEMENTS ON MANUFACTURING OUTPUT IN NIGERIA

Dr Akin George OGUNLEYE ACIB

e-mail: akin.ogunleye@uniosun.edu.ng george.ogunleye@yahoo.co.uk

Telephone: +2348055314633

Lecturer, Department of Economics, Osun State University, Osogbo, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15817544>

Abstract

The paper examines the relationship between foreign exchange rate of the Naira and manufacturing output in Nigeria. These two macroeconomic variables are supposedly interrelated since manufacturing sector clears a segment of the market for foreign exchange and exchange rate as a major consideration in domestic manufacturing sector and domestic output. Using Granger causality and Vector Error Correction modeling (VECM) techniques, the paper found that exchange rate and manufacturing output are independent of each other. The result also revealed that the level of exchange rate has no significant effect on the manufacturing output in Nigeria except in the long run. The paper concludes that exchange rates do influence the real manufacturing sector in the long run and recommends that the current rapid devaluation of naira should be checked by the monetary authority to strengthen the sector towards contributing more to the nation's Gross Domestic Product

Keywords: foreign exchange rate, manufacturing output, error correction modeling, causality, Nigeria

1 Introduction

The economy of Nigeria has undergone several changes in the last few years, most of which are traumatic. In the early 1970s, the economy adopted the Gold Standard by fixing the exchange rate of the currency; this was supported by the increase in the world market price of oil, a major export commodity of Nigeria. The resulting surge in the value of export revenue led to substantial investment in the oil industry and an ensuing improvement in per capita income. Indeed, by the late 1970s, Nigeria became a middle-income country. However, on the cessation of hostilities between the Arabs and the Israelis in the early 1980s, there came a slump in the world oil market, with its concomitant detrimental effect on domestic revenue and a slide in

domestic living standards, which eventually culminated in the overall distortion to the economy. This ugly scenario led to the devaluation of the Nigerian currency against major international currencies, an action that later led to policy shift in exchange rate determination.

The introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986 has brought several innovations in the management of the Nigerian economy. One of the new thinking in the economic management of the country is the floating of the Naira, the nation's currency, the value of which had hitherto been administratively fixed by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The exchange rate of the Naira plays the role of a leading indicator in the economy; this is because fluctuations in exchange rate affects all sectors and indeed all macroeconomic aggregates (Folorunso 2000a & 2000b; Yaqub 2011; Dada and Oyeranti, 2012; Mmaduabuchi and Ifeanyi (2014)), and more particularly the manufacturing sector that also depends on the importation of raw materials and other intermediate products. Indeed, the fluctuations of the exchange rate can result in either depreciation or appreciation under the current free exchange regime in Nigeria, which can have serious implications for the national output.

Countries adopt different types of exchange rate determination, although the specific one is usually dependent on the economic conditions and policy objectives of the imposing country. Not only has Nigeria experimented with both exchange rates, but the nation has equally practiced different forms of floating exchange rate systems for nearly three decades of economic deregulation.

The manufacturing sector plays a significant impact on the economies of developed countries as it accounts for a substantial proportion of total economic activities, whereas, in developing economies and most especially, Nigeria, the sector is responsible for less than 10 percent of total Gross Domestic Product annually. In terms of employment generation, the sector accounts for about 12 percent of the labour force in the formal sector of the nation's economy (National Bureau of Statistics, 2015). In addition to being a real sector, manufacturing plays a catalytic role in the transformation of economies. Thus, a good manufacturing base with high capacity utilization will ordinarily increase a nation's level of productivity, encourage import substitution, create more employment opportunities, and save foreign exchange utilisation on the import of final goods. However, capacity utilisation has been very low in Nigeria, from 47% in 2009 to

45% in 2010 and below 40% in 2022. This gives a cause for concern despite the relative political stability that the country has enjoyed for nearly two decades.

A substantial proportion of the inputs used by the Nigerian manufacturing firms are imported which makes the domestic manufacturing firms highly dependent on the rate of exchange of the country's currency. It is thus expected that the level of exchange rate as well as its movements has role to play in the manufacturing performance and the revenue accruing to the sector.

In relative terms, the share of Nigerian manufacturing output in total GDP has been on the decline over the years. It declined from 9.3% in 1985 to 5.3% in 1995 and further declined to 3.6% in 2000 and later rose marginally to 3.8% in 2005 and 4.3% in 2010 and declined to 3.9% in 2022. In comparison with other sectors, agriculture accounted for up to 50% of GDP in 1970 and declined to about 31% in 2006, while the share of petroleum stood at 8% of GDP in 1970 and rose to nearly 40% of GDP in 2018. The above scenario has implications for the development of the manufacturing sector, a major concern of most budgets over the years.

An exchange rate is defined as the price of one domestic currency in terms of another (the foreign currency). This is different from a cross rate that measures the price of one foreign currency in terms of another foreign currency. The exchange rate tends to be a connecting rod among countries, making it possible to determine the relative value of the goods and services that are produced in different countries. In Nigeria, the exchange rate is defined in terms of the units of the domestic currency per unit of foreign currency. A country's exchange rate has been described as a leading indicator because its value also helps in determining several other macroeconomic variables especially the inflation rate, interest rate, and even money supply.

The situation is however different in Nigeria where a substantial amount of inputs are imported either as raw materials or as intermediate goods. With an appreciation of the local currency, especially under a fixed exchange rate regime, the terms of trade move against the country. With this, the foreign price of manufactured goods rises and become less competitive in the international market. Hence, production and the prospect of manufacturing become hampered by fluctuations in the rate of exchange, either as appreciation or as depreciation.

The above clearly shows that exchange rate fluctuations do affect the output of manufacturing firms, more importantly in Nigeria where a substantial proportion of manufacturing inputs are

imported. Indeed, Nigeria has experimented with fixed exchange rate in the past; however, from September 1986 when the exchange rate was deregulated, there has been a consistent rise in the quantum of Naira per unit of foreign currencies. Under a fixed exchange rate system as was practiced up till September 1986, the CBN used its powers and instruments to determine the exchange rate of the currency, a rate at which all users would have to purchase the quantity of foreign currency needed for transactions. In a floating exchange rate regime, the CBN merely provide an enabling environment that will encourage buyers and sellers to haggle on the appropriate rate of exchange for transactions.

Several problems have also been identified in the literature as hindrances to the growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. For instance, Dipak and Ata (2003) identified these hurdles to include; insecurity, political instability, market-unfriendly state monopolies, weak infrastructural base and inadequate finance. The study by Adenikinju (2003) further found undue bureaucracy and high levels of corruption as deterrents to the growth of the manufacturing sector. It is, however, opined that some poor indicators of macroeconomic aggregates, especially low-capacity utilization, low credit and devaluation of exchange rate experienced in the country might have been partly responsible for the ugly performance of the manufacturing sector in the country. Both studies concluded that the quantum of inputs that can be imported depends on the exchange rate of the currency. Another study by Adenikinju and Chete (2002) confirmed that the problems of the manufacturing sector are compounded by the non-availability of needed intermediate and capital goods that can only be obtained through imports. Consequently, policies that hinder the availability of such imports, or make them more expensive will lead to poor productivity performance. Since the Nigerian manufacturing sector depends largely on imports, then a substantial part of its production capacity would in turn depend on exchange rate fluctuations. This is even more so in a regime of floating exchange rate that Nigeria is operating.

Different forms of exchange rate arrangement have been adopted since 1986 when the Structural Adjustment Programme was introduced in Nigeria. Under the general form of the floating exchange rate, the system started with the Second-tier Foreign Exchange Market (SFEM), to the Autonomous Foreign Exchange Market (AFEM), to the Dutch Auction System (1990-1991), and then the Interbank Foreign Exchange Market (IFEM), and back again to the Dutch Auction System in July 2002; the last variant was with the main purpose of minimising the speculative

tendencies characteristic of authorised foreign exchange dealers. Still arising from the problems of administration, and to further liberalise the market, and thereby narrow the gap between the official and bureau de change rates, and to work towards a convergence of the two rates, while also conserving the nation's foreign reserves, the CBN had to introduce the Wholesale Dutch Auction System (WDAS) in February 2006.

In 1994, a regulation of the foreign exchange market was re-introduced while the rate was fixed by the CBN at N22/US\$1. In February 1995, the AFEM was introduced as a result of the promulgation of Foreign Exchange (Monitoring and Miscellaneous Provisions) Decree 17 of that year; under this arrangement, the CBN was empowered with the ability to intervene in the market at short notice. Arising from the failure of AFEM, the IFEM was introduced in October 1999 with the sole aim of producing a stable exchange rate for the currency. However, negative developments in the foreign exchange market, especially the widening premium between the official and parallel rates and a continuing depletion of foreign exchange reserves led to the abandonment of IFEM and the introduction of Dutch Auction System (DAS) in July 2002. Thus, from 1986 to 2015, vagaries have continued to occur in the exchange rate of the currency.

The causes of fluctuations in the exchange value of the Naira seem more related to the Nigerian situation than general. The country is experiencing low capital utilization with a drop in capacity utilization by more than 80 percent since 2006. This has substantial implications for domestic prices, employment level, balance of payments accounts and more importantly the manufacturing output. Multiple taxes have also been a major bane as manufacturing firms are subject to different types of state and/or federally imposed taxes, which include in the main, Value-Added Tax (VAT) and excise duties. Of greater severity are the problems of power supply and that of accessing alternative sources of energy. Even with the privatization of electricity distribution in Nigeria, available supply is still inadequate and erratic. Fluctuations in exchange rate, be they upward or downward, may not be desirable for manufacturing firms in the country; this is because firms become more open to exchange rate risks and uncertainties as they cannot plan for raw materials and other import requirements.

The paper therefore aims to investigate the effect of the foreign exchange rate on the output of the Nigerian manufacturing sector. The remaining part of the paper is divided into four different sections. Section 2 reviews the literature on foreign exchange rate and manufacturing output

relationship while section 3 focuses on the theoretical framework and model specification as well as analytical techniques employed. Section 4 discusses the empirical findings, while section 5 concludes the paper

2 Review of Literature

The traditional theory of exchange rate views depreciation as a mechanism through which imports could be reduced while exports are promoted; with this, domestic industries producing for export become more competitive in the international market if they can source their raw material inputs locally, while terms of trade may also be favourable. Indeed, combined with import substitution, domestic industries can perform better.

Also, the international trade theory postulates that under a floating exchange rate regime, movements in rates between a foreign currency and the domestic one do affect the ability of firms to import raw materials and other intermediate inputs. For instance, Chacholiades (1985) theorized that depreciation of the home currency promotes the sale of domestic products in the international market as they become relatively cheaper, although the import of inputs becomes more expensive, which in turn harms domestic firms that depend on those inputs. On the other hand, an appreciation of the domestic currency encourages the demand for foreign inputs just as it reduces the nation's international competitiveness and enhances domestic output of the real sector especially that of manufacturing firms. Further study by Ahmad *et al* (2012) examined the relationship between exchange rate uncertainty and imports in Iran. The paper found that foreign exchange rate uncertainty hurts imports, and this is because as real exchange rate increases, the size of imports decreases.

The works of Collin and Mohammed (2024) examine the impact of exchange rate stability on the economic growth of South Africa from 2000 to 2023, the period characterised by significant political and economic changes. The research was designed to investigate if the maintenance of a stable exchange rate can reduce uncertainty in international transactions, foster investor confidence and also support sustainable economic development. Applying Ordinary Least Square on the yearly time series data collected, the findings show that while exchange rate stability positively impacts GDP, the influence of Foreign Direct Investment and political risk is more substantial. The results therefore underscore the need to guarantee a stable economic

environment through sound exchange rate policies and greater efforts at attracting foreign investments towards ensuring long term economic growth.

The research by Okeke et al (2024) studied the interplay between exchange rate dynamics and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria over the period 1995-2022. Data obtained were analysed using the ordinary least square estimation technique. Available findings showed that interest rate does not moderate the negative impact of the exchange rate on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria; this is attributable to the weak interest rate structure of the country. The research thought that monetary authorities should formulate and implement policies that will stabilise exchange rates and also reduce interest rates as a means of enhancing the resilience and growth of the manufacturing sector.

In a study of the growth of manufacturing output in Nigeria, Ac-Ogbonna (2021) examined the impact of fluctuations of macroeconomic variables, particularly exchange rate, lending rates, and inflation rates on the manufacturing output in the country. With the aid of descriptive analysis, findings revealed that macroeconomic instability impacted negatively on the level of manufacturing output. The paper therefore suggested the predictability of major macroeconomic variables as a means of attracting both domestic and foreign investors to the Nigerian manufacturing sector..

Israel (2025) examined the impact of foreign exchange on the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria using disaggregated analysis. With data from secondary materials, and using the Ordinary Least Square regression analysis, the study revealed that during the period 1999-2021, foreign exchange availability had a negative and significant impact on the growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. In a related study, Asaolu (2011) investigated the exposure of listed firms in Nigeria to exchange rate risk using three international currencies namely: the US dollar, the UK pound and the Euro. Findings revealed that those firms are generally exposed to adverse exchange rate risks of the three currencies under investigation, with a higher magnitude of exposure to the US dollar.

Also, Irene et al (2020) investigated the impact of exchange rate volatility on the Nigerian manufacturing sector from 1981 to 2018. Employing the Vector Autoregressive Model in the analysis, the GARCH (1,1) estimates obtained showed that there is persistent volatility associated with the exchange rate. Even after disaggregating manufacturing output into oil-related and non-oil

related, results still confirmed that exchange rate volatility has a significant negative effect on aggregate manufacturing output in Nigeria.

Nwikina et al (2025) also examined the effect of the exchange rate on the performance of Nigeria manufacturing industry during the period, 1985-2022. Annual temporal data were analysed through the unit root test, cointegration test, and the Error Correction model. Findings from the study revealed that real exchange rate had a substantial unfavourable effect on the manufacturing sector GDP in Nigeria while trade openness had a favourable and substantial effect on the sector. Overall, the paper is of the view that government should formulate efficient and feasible trade policies that will liberalise trade and also open the nation's manufacturing sector to foreign investors.

In another study on the exchange rate and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, Orji and Ezeanyaeji (2022) used extensively the canonical cointegration regression framework. The result obtained showed that exchange rate devaluation constrained the manufacturing sector while exchange rate fluctuations hampered manufacturing output. The study suggested that exchange rate management strategies should be allowed to run for a reasonable length, otherwise, too frequent policy changes will continue to have implications for the exchange rate and for any sector that depends on foreign inputs.

Chika et al (2024) investigated the relationship between the exchange rate and Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Adopting the Autoregressive Distributed Lag model for analysis, the findings revealed a negative and insignificant impact of exchange rate and export tax on the manufacturing sector in the long run, while government expenditure has a positive impact also in the long run. Based on these findings, the study recommended the implementation of export promotion, import substitution, capacity utilisation, and effective exchange rate management policies for enhanced productivity

The study of Oladipo et al (2023) focused specifically on investigating the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on Nigerian manufacturing output. Using the Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity technique, findings revealed that while there is no persistence of shocks in the volatility of the exchange rate, the outcome of business cycle stylized facts established that the exchange rate is highly volatile with a negative effect on manufacturing output in Nigeria. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bounds also indicate the existence of the long run relationship between exchange rate and manufacturing output. Similarly, Takpa et al (2023) investigated the

effect of the real exchange rate on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. With the use of Vector Autoregressive Estimates, findings revealed that the real exchange rate had negative and insignificant effect on the manufacturing sector. The study therefore recommends that market forces should be allowed to determine nominal exchange rate.

A study by Mmaduabuchi and Ifeanyi (2014) observed that for an economy that depends on international trade in an era of globalization, the exchange rate becomes a key factor in determining the performance of key sectors. After testing the output performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, it was discovered that there exists a causal relationship between manufacturing output and exchange rate in Nigeria. For the study of Abiola (2025) on the impact of exchange rate volatility on the growth performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria, and after employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag technique, the study revealed a partial effect of exchange rate on the growth of the manufacturing sector. It therefore concluded that exchange rate volatility did not significantly influence the manufacturing sector in Nigeria for the entire study period.

Odey and Agunobi (2023) equally investigates the impact of the exchange rate on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto design, the research employed linear regression analysis to determine the relationship among the variables employed. Considering the smallness of the coefficient of the exchange rate, the study accepted its stated null hypothesis and concluded that the exchange rate has no significant effect on the output of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Effiong et al (2025) also explored the effect of the exchange rate on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag analytical technique, the result revealed that exchange rate and interest rate exerted negative and significant effect on the performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria while bank credit to the sector and government spending exerted a positive and significant effect. The paper eventually suggested that exchange rate stability is necessary to curb the uncertainties associated with the import bill of inputs required by the manufacturing sector.

For the 2019 pandemic, Sugiyanto et al (2022) examined the effect of exchange rate and interest rate on share prices in the manufacturing sector during the COVID-19 era. The results showed that only exchange rate affected manufacturing stock prices while inflation and interest rates did not

Overall, indication from the review of the literature is that while an appreciation of the exchange rate reduces the cost of intermediate inputs, increases domestic supply and enhances capacity utilization, a depreciation of the rate of exchange not only increases the cost of inputs, but more importantly, retards output and create other ripple effects in the economy; these unintended effects include inflationary spirals, shrunken employment and dampened economic prosperity. However, the short run and log run causal relationship between exchange rate movements and manufacturing output has not been adequately addressed in the literature. The paper fills this gap.

3. Theoretical Framework, Model Specification and Analytical Techniques

To determine the effect of foreign exchange rate on manufacturing output in Nigeria, the study relies on the earlier variant of the AK model presented by Harrod (1939) and Domar (1946), which assumes that labour input (L) grows automatically in proportion to capital input (K) and further assumes that aggregate production has fixed technological coefficients which is expressed as:

$$Y = f(L, K) = \min \{ \alpha K, \beta L \} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where α and β are fixed coefficients. Harrod-Domar further postulate that when $\alpha K < \beta L$, firms will minimize cost by producing output given as:

$$Y = AK^\alpha \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Focusing on the manufacturing sector of the economy as a major real sector that engages in production activities and X representing a set of other auxiliary explanatory variables, equation (2) can be expressed as:

$$MO = A(MC^\alpha)(X^{1-\alpha}) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

where MO represents the Manufacturing Output, MC represents the capital employed to produce in the manufacturing sector and A is the level of technology which is assumed to be constant.

From the empirical literature auxiliary explanatory X -variables that influence manufacturing output may include trade openness (TOP), see Bleaney and Fielding (1999)), credit or loan and advances to the manufacturing sector (MLA), see Ajudua and Ojima (2016)), interest rate (INT), exchange rate (EXR), manufacturing capacity utilization (MCU) and oil price (OP) {see Abbas

et al., 2013; Mahboub and Ahmed, 2016}. The inclusion of these auxiliary variables makes equation (3) to be expressed as:

$$MO = A(MC^\alpha EXR^\eta INT^\varphi MLA^\gamma TOP^\theta OP^\vartheta MCU^\omega e) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of equation (4) and focusing on the effect of the foreign exchange rate on manufacturing output, equation (4) can be expressed in a linear form as follows:

$$\dots \ln MO = \phi + \alpha \ln MC + \eta \ln EXR + \varphi \ln INT + \gamma \ln MLA + \theta \ln TOP + \vartheta \ln OP + \omega \ln MCU + \varepsilon \dots (5)$$

where ϕ is the constant term while $\alpha, \eta, \varphi, \gamma, \theta, \vartheta$, and ω are the slope parameters or coefficients of the included explanatory variables in the model and ε is the error term which is assumed to be randomly distributed.

4. Discussion of Findings

Presented here are the results of the estimated model which started with the results of the unit root tests followed by the lag length selection process, then the cointegration tests and the presentation of the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The series included in the model were subjected to stationarity test using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller to avoid spurious regression result. First, we examined the properties of each time series in equation (5) using Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests. These were followed by Johansen cointegration tests to check whether the explanatory variables including exchange rate, cointegrated with the manufacturing output series; that is, whether there exists long-run relationships. In the first step of Johansen cointegration, we estimated both equations using the levels of the series. In the second step, the estimated residuals from the equations were tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests (Engle and Granger, 1987). Finally, equation (5) was estimated using vector error correction modeling techniques in which both the short run and long run relationships between exchange rate and manufacturing output were determined.

The results of unit root tests using Augmented Dickey Fuller Test are shown in Table 1. A maximum lag length of 4 was provided for E-views to automatically select the optimal length which it included. The result showed that all the series are I(1) implying that they became stationary at first difference at 5% level of significance.

Table 1: Results of Unit Root Tests using Augmented Dickey Fuller

Series	ADF Statistic at Level	ADF Statistic at first difference	Remark
<i>lnMO</i>	-0.1107	-5.4641*	I(1)
<i>lnEXR</i>	-1.9907	-4.9595*	I(1)
<i>INT</i>	-2.3705	-5.0471*	I(1)
<i>lnMLA</i>	-0.3113	-4.3863*	• I(1)
<i>TOP</i>	-1.9242	-8.0040*	I(1)
<i>lnOP</i>	-1.0403	-5.2458*	I(1)
<i>lnMC</i>	-0.5280	-3.6834*	I(1)
<i>MCU</i>	-2.1295	-3.6500*	I(1)
5% Critical Statistic	-2.6143	-3.6463	

* represents significance at the 5% level of significance

Source: E-Views Computation

Further, various lag length selection criteria were carried out to test for the optimal lag length for each series in the model using sequential modified LR test statistic, Final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ). The results of the exercise are as presented in Table 2. The results reveal that the optimal lag length adopted for the analysis was one (1) based on the Schwarz information criterion (SIC) while other criteria indicate optimal lag length of two (2).

Table 2: Results of Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	<i>LnL</i>	LR	FPE	AIC	SIC	HQ
0	-467.122	NA	442.493	28.795	29.158	28.917
1	-246.696	320.621	0.0378	19.315	22.580*	20.413
2	-153.182	90.680*	0.0135*	17.526*	23.694	19.601*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion at 5% level

Source: E-Views Computation

Given the condition that all included time series are I(1), with an optimal lag length of one (1), long run cointegration was tested amongst them using Johansen cointegration test and the result reported in Table 3. It was found that there is only one cointegrating equation among the series. As shown in Table 3, the probabilities of the Eigenvalue are significant at 5% and greater than the critical values. Also, trace test indicates 3 cointegrating equations at 5% level of significance. This implies that cointegration existed between manufacturing output and the included explanatory variables. Hence, we proceeded to estimate the long run relationship among the variables using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM).

Table 3: Results of Johansen Cointegration Test

<i>lnMOlnMClnEXR INT lnMLA TOP lnOPlnMCU</i>				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	5% Critical Value	probability**
None *	0.910646	276.3944	159.5297	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.881721	196.6944	125.6154	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.799561	126.2489	95.75366	0.0001
At most 3 *	0.692569	73.20988	69.81889	0.0261
At most 4	0.356106	34.28628	47.85613	0.4862
At most 5	0.305754	19.75897	29.79707	0.4393
At most 6	0.166003	7.716338	15.49471	0.4962
At most 7	0.050959	1.726009	3.841466	0.1889

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level; **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) *p*-values

Source: E-Views Computation

Thus, alongside the VECM estimation, we examined the causal relationship between exchange rate and manufacturing output in Nigeria; the result is presented in Table 4. It is observed from the result that there is neither unidirectional nor bi-directional causal relationship between exchange rate and manufacturing output in Nigeria. This may be interpreted that the two series are independent of each other.

Table 4: Results of VECM Causality Test

Dependent variable: $\Delta(LMO)$				Dependent variable: $\Delta(LER)$			
Excluded	Chi-square Statistic	df	Probability	Excluded	Chi-square Statistic	Df	Probability
$\Delta(lnMC)$	0.443816	1	0.5053	$\Delta(LMO)$	0.057683	1	0.8102
$\Delta(lnEXR)$	0.224691	1	0.6355	$\Delta(LMC)$	0.990016	1	0.3197
$\Delta(INT)$	0.865323	1	0.3523	$\Delta(INT)$	1.287567	1	0.2565
$\Delta(lnMLA)$	6.310588	1	0.0125	$\Delta(LMLA)$	1.418656	1	0.2336
$\Delta(TOP)$	4.640147	1	0.0312	$\Delta(TOP)$	3.7527	1	0.0527
$\Delta(lnOP)$	3.140221	1	0.0764	$\Delta(LOP)$	12.06673	1	0.0005
$\Delta(MCU)$	3.709545	1	0.0541	$\Delta(MCU)$	0.037711	1	0.8462
All	13.579	7	0.0592	All	20.28829	7	0.005

The result of the estimated long run manufacturing output model for Nigeria is shown in Table 5. It is observed that the exchange rate (*lnEXR*) does not portend significant influence on manufacturing output although it shows a negative impact implying that a percentage change in exchange rate reduces manufacturing output by about 0.54%. This result conforms to the *a priori*

sign. The level of capital employed (*lnMC*) is, however, significant at 1% while interest rate (INT) is insignificant in explaining manufacturing output although, both have positive effect on manufacturing output. Thus, a percentage increase in *lnMC* and INT will bring about a 2.09% and 0.04% increase in manufacturing output respectively. Manufacturing loans and advances (*lnMLA*), oil price (*lnOP*), trade openness (TOP) and manufacturing capacity utilization (MCU) exhibit a negative relationship with manufacturing output. While *lnMLA* is significant at 1%, *lnOP*, TOP and MCU are shown to be insignificant determinants of manufacturing output. However, a percentage increase in *lnMLA*, *lnOP* and MCU reduces manufacturing output by 2.1%, 0.40% and 0.02%, respectively while a unit increase in TOP reduces manufacturing output by 2.7%.

Table 5: Result of Estimate Long Run Model of Manufacturing Output in Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
<i>LnMC</i>	2.092837***	0.626187	3.342189	0.0025
<i>LnEXR</i>	-0.54296	0.553136	-0.981599	0.3353
INT	0.041371	0.062509	0.661844	0.5139
<i>LnMLA</i>	-2.10072***	0.659400	-3.185809	0.0037
<i>LnOP</i>	-0.40156	0.870797	-0.461143	0.6485
TOP	-0.0274	0.019321	-1.418247	0.1680
MCU	-0.01909	0.026781	-0.712937	0.4822
C	-54.7972***	17.40515	-3.148334	0.0041
TREND	0.698345***	0.093086	7.502149	0.0000
R-square	0.854333	Mean dependent var	3.928111	
Adjusted R-square	0.809512	S.D. dependent var	2.661232	
S.E. of regression	1.161492	Akaike info criterion	3.354322	
Sum squared resid	35.07564	Schwarz criterion	3.754268	
Log likelihood	-49.7006	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.492383	
F-statistic	19.06116	Durbin-Watson stat	1.87792	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000	Prob(Wald F-statistic)	0.0000	

*** represents significant at 1% level of significance

The diagnostic tests for this model reveal that the included variables jointly explain manufacturing output off 1% level of significance to the tune of 79.52% (R^2); when the degree of freedom is considered, the variables explain 74.21% (R^2 adjusted) of variation in manufacturing output. The model is, however, deficient since it contains serial correlation of both first and second order and contains heteroskedasticity although the residuals are normally distributed and the CUSUM result shows a stable model as reported in Table 6.

Table 6: Results of Diagnostic Tests on the Estimated Long Run Model

Diagnostic Test	Test Statistics	Probability	Remark
Serial Autocorrelation	10.55272	0.0051	Serial Correlation
Heteroskedasticity	12.93741	0.0736	Heteroskedasticity
Normality Test	0.2232	0.8943	Residuals Normal
Stability Test (CUSUM)	Stable		

Since the series are I(1) and there are 3 co-integrating equations, an error correction model that combines both the short run and long run relationship was estimated and the result reported in Table 7. Only the lag of the first error correction term [ECM1(-1)] satisfies the statistical conditions that its coefficient must be less than unity (1) in absolute terms and negatively significant. Thus, it implies that the speed of adjustment is approximately 47.09% indicating only 47.09% of past errors are corrected in the current period. The level of manufacturing output in the previous period is seen to positively impact the current level of output in the manufacturing sector such that a percentage increase in the last period's manufacturing output leads to a 0.16% increase in current manufacturing output. However, its coefficient result is not significant. As for capital employed, a one percentage increase in capital employed produces a negative effect on manufacturing output such that it reduces manufacturing output by 0.73%. This, also, is not significant in explaining manufacturing output.

Interest rate bears a negative effect on manufacturing output. This brings to bear that as interest rate increases by 1%, manufacturing output reduces by 8.5%. This result is only significant at a 10% level of significance. However, loans and advances to the manufacturing sector, trade openness, oil price and manufacturing capacity utilization portend significant effect on manufacturing output in Nigeria. Specifically, a percentage increase in loans and advances to the manufacturing sector result in the reduction of manufacturing output by 3.34% and 1.33%, respectively while, a unit change in trade openness and manufacturing capacity utilization increases manufacturing output to the tune of 0.04% and 0.11%, respectively.

With regards to the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on manufacturing output, it was discovered that a percentage increase in the exchange rate in the previous period leads to an increase in the output of the manufacturing sector by 0.5% in the short run. The coefficient is, however, insignificant. This means that as exchange rate appreciates, importation of physical

equipment is encouraged and thus enhances the use of local raw materials in the manufacturing sector which then increases output in that sector.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) reported indicates that in the short run, only 48.0% approximately of the variation in manufacturing output is explained although F-statistics shows that the variables are not jointly significant in explaining variation in manufacturing output. Further, and as shown in Table 8, the result indicates that the model does not contain autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity but the residual lacks normality.

Table 7: Result of Estimate ECM Model of Manufacturing Output in Nigeria

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECM1(-1)	-0.47086***	0.166685	-2.82483	0.0101
ECM2(-1)	2.133785	1.479907	1.441837	0.1641
ECM3(-1)	-0.46914	0.961731	-0.48781	0.6307
$\Delta(\ln MO(-1))$	0.165583	0.181977	0.909913	0.3732
$\Delta(\ln MC(-1))$	-0.72868	1.093795	-0.6662	0.5125
$\Delta(\ln EXR(-1))$	0.495049	1.044373	0.474016	0.6404
$\Delta(\text{INT}(-1))$	-0.06926	0.074457	-0.93023	0.3628
$\Delta(\ln MLA(-1))$	-3.34061**	1.329812	-2.51209	0.0202
$\Delta(\text{TOP}(-1))$	0.042255**	0.019616	2.1541	0.0430
$\Delta(\ln OP(-1))$	-1.33379*	0.752676	-1.77207	0.0909
$\Delta(\text{MCU}(-1))$	0.109537*	0.056872	1.926018	0.0677
CONSTANT	0.839494	0.359644	2.334237	0.0296
R-square	0.479842	Mean dependent var	0.208221	
Adjusted R-square	0.207379	S.D. dependent var	0.044935	
S.E. of regression	0.930299	Akaike info criterion	2.968665	
Sum squared resid	18.17456	Schwarz criterion	3.512850	
Log likelihood	-36.98300	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.151767	
F-statistic	1.761124	Durbin-Watson stat	1.682830	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.127533			

*, ** and *** represents 10%, 5% and 1% level of significance respectively.

Source: E-Views Computation

Table 8: Results of Diagnostics Tests on ECM Model

	Test Statistics	Probability	Remark
Portmanteau Autocorrelation	2.7436	0.2537	No serial Correlation
Heteroskedasticity	26.8794	0.0428	No Heteroskadasticity

Normality Test	64.9712	0.000	Not Normal
Stability Test (CUSUM)	Stable		

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper examined the nexus between the foreign exchange rate and manufacturing output in Nigeria using the vector error correction modeling (VECM) technique. Although the paper confirmed the independent nature of both the foreign exchange rate and manufacturing output in the country, it nevertheless discovered the presence of cointegration between manufacturing output and its identified explanatory variables. Since the effect of capital employed is significant, manufacturing firms should step up their efforts at sourcing for greater capital particularly from the capital market. At the revealed level of sensitivity of manufacturing output to interest rate, any further increase in lending rates above the present threshold may greatly impact manufacturing productivity.

In conclusion, the level of exchange rate does not have a significant effect on the manufacturing output in Nigeria except in the long run and thus recommends that the current rapid devaluation of Nigerian currency should be checked by the monetary authority. This will further assist the sector and encourage more investments from foreign countries.

References

- babes, R., Fateme, H. & Alireza, B. (2013), The effects of oil price shocks on real GDP in Iran, *African Journal of Business Management*, 7(33), (September), 3220 – 3232
- Abiola, O.M (2025). Impact of Exchange rate volatility on the manufacturing Sector Growth Performance in Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Arts and Social Science* 13 (1) 1-9
- Ac-Ogbonna, C. (2021). Fluctuations of Macroeconomic Variables and Manufacturing Output: Issues, Challenges and Prospects of the Growth of Manufacturing Output in Nigeria. *Bullion*, 45 (3), 30-43
- Adenikinju, A. (2003), Nigeria's imperative in the new world trade order. Workshop Report; *African Economics Research Consortium, Nairobi, Kenya and Trade Policy Research and Training (TPRTP)*, Department of Economics, University of Ibadan.
- Adenikinju, A. & Chete, L. (2002), Productivity, market structure and trade liberalization in Nigeria, Economics Development Department, NISER; *AERC Research Paper 126, Africa Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi (November)*.
- Ahmad, J. S., Mehdi, A. & Negin, H. (2012), Exchange rate uncertainty and imports; evidence from Iran, *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 11(2), 167-172

- Ajudua, E. I. & Ojima, D. (2016), Modeling the determinants of output in the Nigerian Manufacturing Sector, *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 4(1), (January – March), 1-12.
- Asaolu, T. O. (2011), Exchange rate risk explosive of Nigeria listed firms: An empirical examination, *International Business Research*, 4(2), (April), 219-225.
- Bleaney, M. & Fielding, D. (1999), Exchange rate regimes, inflation and output volatility in developing countries, *CREDIT Research Paper No. 99/4*
- Chacholiades, M. (1985), *International trade theory and policy*, McGraw Hill International Book Company
- Chika, P.I, Chika M.O, Irene H. O, & Chike K.O (2024).Exchange rate fluctuations and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria: Issues and implication for economic recovery. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science VII (xi)*
- Collin, C. & Mohammed I.J. (2024). Analysis of exchange rate stability on the economic growth of a developing country: The case of South Africa from 2000 to 2023. *Economies*, 12:296
- Dada, E. A. & Oyeranti O. A. (2012), Exchange rate and macroeconomic aggregates in Nigeria *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 3(2), 93-100.
- Dipak, M. and Ata, M. (2003), *The African manufacturing firm, an analysis based on firm studies in sub-Sahara Africa*, Taylor and Francis Ltd
- Effiong U. E. (2025). Foreign exchange market and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*. 6 (1) 50-74
- Engle, R. F. and Granger, C. W. J. (1987), Co-integration and error correction: representation, estimation, and testing, *Econometrica*, 55(2), pp. 251-276.
- Folorunso, B. A. (2000a),The impact of exchange rate devaluation on trade in Nigeria (1986-1997), *Journal of the Nigerian Anthropological and Sociological Association*, 1(1), (October), 153-166.
- Folorunso, B. A. (2000b),An Empirical investigation of the relationship between currency devaluation and inflation in Nigeria (1970-1998), *The Nigerian Economic and Financial Review*, 5(2), (December), 77- 89.
- Irene, N.O, Obi K. O, Ezenekwe U.R & Ukeji C D. (2020). Effect of exchange rate volatility on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, VIII (3) 345-359
- Israel, K. E. (2025). Foreign exchange and the performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria: A disaggregated analysis. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*.25 (2) 14- 23
- Mahboub, A. A. & Ahmed H. E. (2016), The effect of oil price shocks on the Saudi manufacturing sector, *Topics in Middle Eastern and African Economies*, 18(2), (September), 1-14.

- Mmaduabuchi, E. F. & Ifeanyi, A. E. (2014), Exchange rate and manufacturing performance in Nigeria, *Journal of Empirical Economics*, 3(6), 352-61
- National Bureau of Statistics (2015), Nigeria MDGs Performance Survey Report 2015/UNDP in Nigeria, Abuja
- Nwikina C.G. Elizabeth, O. W, Kenigheni, G. W, & Mathew F. E (2025). Exchange rate and performance of manufacturing industry in Nigeria. *Global Academic Journal of Economics and Business*. 7 (1) 28-39
- Odey, P.O & Agunobi, C.C (2023). Effect of exchange rate on the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. *AFIT Journal of Marketing Research* 3
- Okene, A. J, Steve N.J, & Ifeanyi O. U (2024). Effects of exchange rate on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria : A time series analysis with a focus on interest rate dynamics. *African Banking and Finance Review Journal* 8 (8) 14-27
- Oladipo O. R, Ademola A. O, Oluwafolakemi A & Ogunjobi O.(2023). Exchange rate fluctuations and manufacturing output: Stylized evidence in Nigeria. *Development Management*, 22 (3) 32-42
- Orji, M.C & Ezeanyaeji C.I (2022). Exchange rate and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria *Lapai Journal of Economics* 6 (2)
- Sugiyanto, I. Sugiyanto, Rima E. O., Toufiq A, P, & Endra H. (2022) The effect of exchange rate and interest rate on share prices in the manufacturing sector with inflation as moderation. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Kontemporer*, 14 (2) 226-236
- Takpa B. S, Chukwu, K O, & Akunna C. R (2023). Real exchange rate and manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy: 1999- 2021. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation* 4 (3) 691-697
- Yaqub, J.O. (2011), Anticipated and unanticipated exchange rate changes and output performance in Nigeria: an empirical analysis, *Journal of Economic Theory*, 5(4), 84-92